

Towards Cross-Domain Linking of Data: A Semantic Mapping of Cultural Heritage Ontologies

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ABSTRACT

The Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) registry, designed with the Linked Data principles at core, provides an environment suitable for research which targets domain-specific, but also potentially reusable, information representation. The main purpose of this study is to follow the recommendations pertaining to the utilisation of LOV as a basis for experimentation in order to examine how information within the Cultural Heritage (CH) domain can be improved in terms of reusability and interoperability. The present lack of cross-domain knowledge transfer forms the motivation behind this study, with the aim of facilitating the transition from conventional, domain-specific knowledge representation to reusable and semantically interoperable information. The methodology of this study involves the manual semantic mapping of elements from 12 vocabularies in the LOV registry, reinforced by a small-scale experiment using contemporary large language models (LLMs), particularly GPT, for a preliminary assessment of the mapping process. The findings revealed several key aspects to consider regarding the alignment of semantically adjacent vocabulary elements in the CH domain and beyond, emphasising the potential unveiled by linking domain-focused schemata to standardised, established ones while preserving the conceptual hierarchies inherent to each individual knowledge domain. The contribution of this research pertains to the vision of linking data across different domains by initiating the alignment among representation schemata in CH, with the ultimate aim to expand beyond the boundaries of the in-word knowledge domain, while employing combinatory methodological approaches of technological means and human expertise to facilitate this process.

CCS CONCEPTS

• semantic interoperability; • linked open vocabularies; • cultural heritage; • ontology mapping; • LLMs; • GPT; • reusability; • linked open data; • cross-domain interoperability;

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1 INTRODUCTION

The quest for standardisation of knowledge representation within and across domains remains at core when the semantic interoperability and reusability of existing representation schemata are being addressed. The Linked Data principles [1] as one of the most important pillars of the Semantic Web, remain pivotal for structured data publication and the integration of information derived from disparate sources on the Web or across different platforms. The importance of standardisation and reuse has already been emphasized by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) in their Best Practices regarding data vocabularies and the potential to identify terms from shared vocabularies for (meta)data encoding [2]. More specifically, Best Practice 15 mentions the contribution and impact of vocabulary reuse on interoperability and the emergence of Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) [3] as a “testbed” for research in this regard. Consensus among publishers, consumers, and other stakeholders involved in the process of making data publicly available is an important aspect to be pursued as the need for standardisation and semantically interoperable datasets and information is continuously growing.

The main purpose of this study is to follow the recommendations pertaining to the utilisation of the Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) registry as a basis for experimentation and as a facilitator for reuse, in order to examine how information within the Cultural Heritage (CH) domain can be improved in terms of reusability, interoperability and, consequently, even findability. The LOV ecosystem, designed with the Linked Data principles at core, provides an environment suitable for research which targets domain-specific, but also potentially reusable across domains, information representation. The existing research on LOV and the variety of implementations in different contexts, is a good demonstration of the potential of this increasingly intriguing tool. Furthermore, the reusability of vocabularies across different knowledge areas is an expanding topic of interest, with research on reusability and interoperability measurements playing a major role in this regard. Within the context

of this study is to focus on the Cultural Heritage domain, examine the current situation among the existing relevant vocabularies in LOV, how information in this domain is currently represented by the different existing ontologies and vocabularies, and what is the potential to allow for inter-domain reuse and semantic interoperability to shift towards standardisation in this specific domain by mapping common elements in the schemata of a chosen set of vocabularies. All things considered, the research question the present study seeks to answer is: given a custom metadata schema in the Cultural Heritage domain, how can it be mapped to existing, known schemata to be semantically interoperable across more knowledge domains? The contribution of this piece of research pertains to the vision of linking data across different domains by initiating an attempt to map main representation schemata in the Cultural Heritage domain and beyond, based on Linked Open Vocabularies and ontologies. Additionally, this research, building on existing knowledge of this domain, explores the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) to map similar attributes across different vocabularies, offering a novel approach to enhance semantic interoperability and facilitate more efficient data integration and knowledge discovery across varied domains.

The study is structured as follows: the Background Section includes related literature as the foreground of the conducted work, the Methodology Section presents and describes the steps followed to approach this research, and the Results Section includes the presentation of outcomes after the described methodology had been applied. Following these Sections, the Discussion Section includes the analysis of the findings and benchmarking against existing research, while the Future Directions Section describes the lines of research deriving from this study and potential continuation of this study for further development and improved results.

2 RELATED WORK

Regarding semantic interoperability, vocabulary development, and Linked Open Data (LOD) technologies in the cultural heritage domain, various approaches with rich scientific foundation have been deployed. Marlet et al. (2019) [4] delved into the challenges and methodologies for achieving semantic interoperability in archaeology, a field closely linked to cultural heritage. Their work underscores the importance of Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) in creating a unified framework for integrating diverse datasets, directly informing the practical approaches for mapping cultural heritage vocabularies. This research work is directly relevant to the present study since it provides insights into practical approaches for mapping cultural heritage vocabularies for enhanced interoperability. The concept of interlinking digital heritage objects through specifically designed vocabularies is further explored by Marcondes in his 2018 and 2020 studies [5], [6], highlighting the potential of LOD technologies in establishing connections based on culturally relevant relationships and provides a solid foundation for effective cultural heritage data representation.

The need for standards and tools to enable cross-domain data interoperability in heritage science and cultural heritage is addressed by Castelli et al. (2021) [7], who focus on overcoming technical and semantic challenges in integrating heterogeneous data sources. This approach aligns with the need for standardized semantic mapping and interoperability, resonating with this study's objectives.

Complementing these insights, Longo et al. (2020) [8] discuss strategies for enhancing knowledge accessibility and networking through interoperable open platforms in cultural heritage. Their research provides insights into the strategic planning and implementation of interoperable systems, which are critical for the successful integration of cultural heritage data across various domains. Piedra et al. (2020) [9] contribute to this discourse by exploring the use of linked data and musical information to enhance knowledge management in the cultural heritage sector. Their research showcases the practical applications of linking diverse datasets, including musical information, enriching the domain. An earlier study by Isaac et al. (2007) [10] already laid the ground in this area by focusing on aligning thesauri for integrated access to cultural heritage resources, offering valuable methodologies for aligning different vocabularies. Simou et al. (2017) [11] address another critical aspect of cultural heritage – its digitisation and aggregation. They focus on major cultural portals like Europeana and advocate for the implementation of LOD principles to enhance information representation and metadata quality. De Boer et al. (2012) [12] demonstrated a methodology for transforming cultural heritage metadata into Linked Open Data, using the Amsterdam Museum as a case study.

In the context of vocabulary alignment, Tordai et al. (2010) [13] explore the alignment of large, language-specific vocabularies, providing insights into achieving precision and recall in this process. Marcondes (2021) [14] also contributes significantly by proposing a framework for implementing culturally relevant relationships between digital collections in cultural heritage institutions, emphasizing the use of vocabularies to establish these connections. Hellmund et al. (2018) [15] introduce the HERACLES Ontology, aimed at managing cultural heritage in a further contemporary context, integrating diverse domains and employing LOD technologies for interdisciplinary heritage management and preservation. Križaj et al. (2022) [16] present a more recent perspective with their preliminary findings on reconciling vocabularies related to monuments, museums, and gallery objects, addressing the challenges and strategies in harmonizing different vocabularies, which is crucial for identifying similarities among them. Maratsi et al. (2023) [17] emphasize the importance of standardisation in representing cultural heritage information on the Web, particularly in describing (folklore) museum artifacts in the digital realm. They also highlight how custom metadata models and disparate data sources can hinder the findability, interoperability, but also visibility (especially from a cultural heritage site perspective) of related information.

In a similar vein but with shifted focus towards the legal domain, Loutsaris et al. (2023) [18] investigate interoperability by mapping two core ontologies of the domain, the European Legislation Identifier (ELI) and Akoma Ntoso (AKN) ontologies and following the Linked Open Legal Data concept. The mapping in this case was performed manually, validated by tools, and, finally, evaluated by domain experts. Similar to this approach by Loutsaris et al. (2023) [18], in the present study the initial mapping is conducted manually, in order to later on be validated and evaluated using algorithmic, human, and mixed methods. Extending this research, the present study also builds upon the recent analysis of Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) and their potential for reusability and interoperability by Maratsi et al. (2023) [19], with the main aim to, this time, focus on the cultural heritage domain, map vocabularies and identify connections to adjacent knowledge fields for cross-domain data linking.

Figure 1: The methodological process followed for the mapping of the LOV vocabularies.

Furthermore, in recent research on using Large Language Models (LLMs) to identify similarities in attributes across different ontologies, significant advancements have been noted in semantic feature verification and qualitative research applications of LLMs. These studies demonstrate the capabilities of LLMs in parsing and analyzing complex datasets to uncover semantic relationships. However, they also highlight several limitations, including the inherent biases of LLMs, the substantial computational resources required, and the challenges in capturing nuanced semantic meanings accurately. These research efforts underscore the basic requirements for implementing these models, such as the necessity for extensive corpora and specific data formats to train the models effectively. In addition, methodologies for assessing semantic similarity among entity classes from different ontologies have been developed, presenting a promising approach to ontology analysis. Despite these advancements, the dynamic nature of ontologies and ambiguities in attributes pose ongoing challenges. These findings collectively underscore the potential of LLMs in semantic analysis while emphasizing the need for addressing issues related to model accuracy, computational demands, and the interpretation of domain-specific nuances in future research [20], [21], [22], [23].

3 METHOD

The methodology followed in the context of the present study is described in this Section. The main purpose is to assess the semantic proximity of selected vocabularies from the LOV ecosystem in order to reveal their potential of semantic interoperability and reusability within and across the Cultural Heritage domain. The approach towards this study is predominantly based on the manual mapping of proximal elements of the vocabularies' schemata, including a number of preparatory steps followed before reaching the actual mapping process. An additional methodological step regarding a preliminary assessment of the mapping process is included at the end of this Section. An overview of the complete methodological approach for this study is shown in Figure 1.

To begin with, the identification of existing cultural heritage ontologies and vocabularies was necessary for the initiation of the process. The authors exhaustively searched through the 829 vocabularies available in the LOV ecosystem in order to identify

vocabularies directly, indirectly, and remotely relevant to the cultural heritage domain. The LOV vocabularies included in the study were vocabularies which bear direct or indirect relation to CH, which means the selection included those which commonly belong to other knowledge domains but can at the same time be referred to from a cultural heritage context (e.g., geospatial, temporal, storytelling, environment, linguistics, food, academia, geometry, architecture, music etc.). This process resulted in 104 vocabularies.

As a next step, the 104 vocabularies chosen were shortlisted according to their proximity in relation to the CH domain. In the context of this study, the authors selected a small sample of the vocabularies to conduct further, manual semantic analysis on. The shortlisting of the vocabularies was based on the structure of their schema and content described, and it resulted in the selection of 12 vocabularies, 6 directly related to the CH domain, 4 indirectly related, and 2 remotely related to CH (vocabularies which are normally used outside the CH context). This selection was additionally influenced by factors such as the popularity of the vocabulary in this domain, its number of links to other vocabularies, and the closer proximity potential based on its schema. The selected vocabularies (ecrm, cevent, cis, edm, a-loc, ctlog, bio, lode, eac-cpf, eclap, donto, and time) and their descriptions are shown in Figure 2. The rationale behind this selection was to include vocabularies both directly and indirectly related to CH in order to examine manually the common elements they might share and how those could be mapped to each other. The manual mapping of vocabularies can offer the opportunity for direct human evaluation, however, due to the complexity of relations and time-consuming one-to-one comparisons, the number of vocabularies to be included in the process is limiting, although a good starting point to serve as the ground for more advanced experimentation to take place afterwards and include all the identified vocabularies (e.g., machine learning).

After the selection of the vocabularies for analysis, the authors proceeded to the preparation for manual semantic mapping of the common elements identified. For this purpose, the schema for each vocabulary was examined (typically in the Notation3/ N3 representation available). For the present analysis, all the classes of the vocabularies were retrieved. Classes in RDF are typically defined using triples of the form subject predicate object where the subject is the class, so in our case all the classes were retrieved

ecrm	ecrm- Erlangen CRM/OWL. An OWL DL implementation of the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model.
cevent	Cultural Event Ontology (ArCo network), e.g., events involving cultural properties.
cis	Cultural-ON (Cultural ONtology): Cultural Institute/Site and Cultural Event Ontology. Models CH data, such as data regarding the agents that play a specific role on cultural institutes or sites.
edm	The Europeana Data Model vocabulary, an integration medium for collecting, connecting and enriching the descriptions provided by Europeana data providers.
a-loc	Location Ontology (ArCo network). Models information related to the localization and georeferencing of a cultural property.
ctlog	Catalogue Ontology (ArCo network). Allows the description of concepts related to the Italian General Catalogue of Cultural Heritage, and in particular catalogue records, recording all data gathered by a cataloguer on a particular cultural property.
bio	A vocabulary for biographical information about people.
lode	Linking Open Descriptions of Events. An ontology for publishing descriptions of historical events as Linked Data, and for mapping between other event-related vocabularies and ontologies.
eac-cpf	Descriptions Ontology for Linked Archival Data. Encoded Archival Context for Corporate Bodies, Persons, and Families, provides a grammar for encoding names of creators of archival materials and related information.
eclap	Performing Arts Vocabulary. Provides classes and properties for the description of multimedia content related to performing arts.
donto	Dataset Ontology. An OWL ontology designed to describe the characteristics of datasets published on data.gov.au.
time	Time Ontology. Defines temporal entities such as time intervals, their properties and relationships.

Figure 2: The selected vocabularies/ontologies to be included in the semantic analysis.

using the search term “owl:Class” within the N3 document for each. All the classes were then organised in tabular form; the table including exhaustively all the classes of the 12 vocabularies as rows and columns in order to perform the one-to-one mappings of the elements. The mapping Table finally consisted of 442 elements (the vocabulary classes), as rows and columns. For the mapping process, the authors followed the rules below:

- Each element of the Table columns is compared against each element of each Table row.
- The diagonals of the mapping table which annotated the same fields of the same vocabulary were filled with the symbol “III” (e.g., E21_Person with E21_Person). Obviously, no mapping can be performed for such pairs, as we are referring to identity.
- The intersections of fields of the same vocabulary that cannot be mapped were filled with the symbol “0” (e.g., E21_Person with E39_Actor). This is to show comparisons which do not make sense and would be wrongful.
- The symbol “X” is filled at the intersections where a potential mapping is. This X is indicated in colours for relevance strength (green and yellow). The mapping rationale in this case (between elements of different vocabularies) is very strict; indicating only direct mapping referring to the same

or very proximal elements (according to the schema description), so it indicates almost direct interchangeability.

- The symbol “Y” is filled in for mappings within the same vocabulary that could be referring to similar things. The mapping rationale here (between elements of the same vocabulary) is more lenient to indicate similar, subsets, or supersets of elements and to capture the loose relationships of similar elements as well.
- Apparently when a mapping symbol is assigned for a relationship (“III”, “0”, “X” or “Y”), the same symbol is directly assigned to the symmetric relationship on the mapping Table. So, if element A is mapped to element B, element B will also be mapped to element A using the same symbolic annotation.

In addition:

- Special attention is given to unique elements of the mapping Table; this could be an indication for the description of a niche domain or could offer special semantic value.
- Special attention is given to fields used by other known vocabularies (e.g., dcat, skos, voaf, foaf, etc.); this could give useful leads towards the wider use of core, already standardized vocabulary fields. The mappings which involve fields of such vocabularies are indicated in the mapping Table by

Figure 3: Methodological Framework for analyzing Cultural Heritage Vocabularies using LLMs.

the symbol “X (CORE)”. The X (CORE) mappings are also indicated in colours for relevance strength (green and yellow).

The manual mapping process of the vocabularies comes with a few hinders and considerations. For instance, due to the lack of sufficient descriptive information in the data schemata of the chosen vocabularies, the comparison between certain elements (classes) was impossible. In general, the elimination rules followed in the mapping process were that no mapping comparison was conducted unless sufficient information on the description of the field was included in the data schema, and that more obvious mapping possibilities were annotated for the cases that this was feasible. In addition, the comparison for potential mapping was mainly feasible for elements of the same hierarchy depth. The extraction of classes from the vocabulary schema implies the study of flat and contextual metadata, and this is the focus of the present study’s scope.

3.1 Preliminary Assessment of the Mapping Process using LLMs

In addition to the methodological process described, a smaller experiment for a preliminary assessment of the conducted manual mappings was included. More specifically, the authors employed one of the contemporary LLMs (GPT 3.5 and GPT 4) to automate the process of finding similar attributes across vocabularies. To facilitate this process, vocabularies from the legal domain were chosen as examples for prompt engineering and tuning following the results by Loutsaris et al., (2023) [18]. The reason behind this choice is that the study conducted by Loutsaris et al., (2023) also involved a manual mapping between two core legal ontologies, but the results were also validated by tools and evaluated by domain experts, so their mappings could assist in instructing the employed LLM to follow a similar approach in this case.

The methodology employed the LLMs by engineering the prompts to compare the classes of three prominent CH vocabularies. The objective was to identify similarities that would enable their interchangeable use. This comparative analysis was conducted under different conditions to evaluate the effectiveness of the models: zero-shot, and few-shot (three and six). As illustrated in Figure 3, the methodology comprised the following steps:

- 1) Selection of Cultural Heritage Vocabularies: The methodology began with the selection of three prominent cultural heritage vocabularies. These vocabularies were chosen for their significance and diversity, ensuring a comprehensive analysis.
- 2) Construction of Prompt: This step involved crafting specific prompts for GPT-4 and GPT-3.5. The prompts were designed to guide the models in accurately comparing the selected vocabularies and identifying similar classes. The data was provided in a structured textual format which proved to be significantly intuitive.
- 3) Comparative Analysis Using Language Models: This critical step encompassed three distinct sub-steps, each employing a different learning approach:
 - a) Zero-Shot Learning: The model analysed the vocabularies without any prior examples, relying solely on their pre-trained knowledge to identify similarities.
 - b) Three-Shot Learning: The model was provided with three examples of matching from the legal domain to enhance its understanding of ontology matching and improve the accuracy of the comparative analysis.
 - c) Six-Shot Learning: This stage involved giving the models six examples from the legal domain, aiming to see how a larger set of contextual data influences the depth and nuance of the analysis.

Figure 4: General information about the identified mappings.

- 4) Comparison with Manual Mapping: The last step was to compare the results generated by the AI models with those obtained through the manual mapping and similarity analysis. This comparison facilitated the validation of model results and understanding of models’ capabilities in relation to traditional methods.

In the following Section, the detailed results of the performed semantic mapping of the selected CH vocabularies are presented and analysed, including the sub-section of the LLM indicative results.

4 RESULTS

The present study focused on the manual mapping among the 443 classes belonging to a sample of 12 vocabularies, as described in the Method Section. The conducted analysis resulted in a total of 386 “X” and “X (CORE)” (including both yellow and green) mappings among the chosen vocabulary classes. As described previously, the yellow annotation indicates a more loose, potential mapping between the elements, while the green annotation indicates a stronger potential match. In further detail, the annotation “X (CORE)” refers to potential matches among classes belonging to core vocabularies (e.g., dcat, skos, foaf, etc.). A total of 52 “X (CORE)” (including both yellow and green) potential mappings were identified, of which 16 green, and 36 yellow matches. As far as the stronger candidates for potential mapping (green annotation) is concerned, 122 cases were identified. The summary of the aforementioned statistics is shown in Figure 4. The mappings which were predominantly considered in the analysis are the X mappings (which include both the yellow-loose and green-strong match candidates), the Green X mappings (the strong match candidates) and X (CORE) mappings, which are a small percentage of the sample but since they include the potential for the inclusion and reuse of core vocabulary fields, they are deemed of great importance in this study.

As far as the mappings among the examined vocabularies are concerned, Table 1 includes the total number of pair-wise mappings of classes among the LOV vocabularies. For instance, between the vocabularies ecrm (an OWL implementation of the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model) and cevent (Cultural Event Ontology for

cultural properties), 16 potential mappings were identified (including both green-strong and yellow-loose mappings), while between edm (the Europeana Data Model vocabulary) and a-loc (the ontology for localisation and georeferencing of a cultural property), 8 potential mappings were noted. This table is an upper triangular matrix due to the symmetric nature of the pair-wise matches. As described in the Method Section, 6 of the vocabularies selected are directly related to the CH domain, the other 6 are remotely related to the domain, and the rationale behind this is to initiate experimentation with mappings which span across various knowledge domains. As can be seen in the Tables of the Results Section, due to this characteristic, the number of potential mappings can be lower for the last 6 vocabularies, although this is not necessarily the case for more comprehensive ontologies (such as ecrm) which implies that semantically adjacent elements can exist across significantly different domains, a hypothesis that forms the core of this research.

Similarly, Table 2 demonstrates the number of potential mappings among the LOV vocabularies but focuses solely on the X (CORE) cases of matches, that is, the cases which include potential matches with fields of core vocabularies (e.g., dcat, skos, foaf, etc.). As expected, the numbers here are significantly smaller considering that, with a few exceptions which predominantly reuse fields of core vocabularies, the majority have their own schema and use their own classes. If not sufficient information for class description exists in the schema, the mapping with potential core candidates becomes more difficult to identify. In general, the reuse of fields from core vocabularies is not as high as it could be for the majority of the examined vocabularies.

In closer view of the identified potential mappings, Table 3 shows an excerpt of vocabulary fields which were predominantly mapped to fields of other vocabularies, along with the number of instances of those potential mappings. The columns “number of X (green) mappings” and “number of X (CORE) mappings” denote how many of the initial number refer to stronger (green) mappings and how many refer to CORE mappings respectively, while the last column shows the number of vocabularies the field in word has potential to be mapped to (to respective field(s) of the other vocabulary). For instance, ecrm’s class “E21_Person” could potentially be mapped

Table 1: Total number of X mappings (green and yellow) among the LOV vocabularies.

VOCABS: X Mappings	cevent	cis	edm	a-loc	ctlog	bio	lode	eac-cpf	eclap	donto	time
ecrm	16	9	1	3	1	7	7	11	9	3	1
cevent	0	10	1	3	2	12	10	9	7	3	4
cis	-	0	1	8	3	7	5	5	2	3	3
edm	-	-	0	8	3	3	3	2	1	1	1
a-loc	-	-	-	0	5	4	3	8	2	3	3
ctlog	-	-	-	-	0	2	1	5	2	2	1
bio	-	-	-	-	-	0	1	1	1	1	1
lode	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	1	2	1	1
eac-cpf	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	5	3	3
eclap	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	3	3
donto	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	2
time	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0

Table 2: Total number of X (CORE) mappings (green and yellow) among the LOV vocabularies.

VOCABS: X (CORE) Mappings	cevent	cis	edm	a-loc	ctlog	bio	lode	eac-cpf	eclap	donto	time
ecrm	8	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
cevent	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
cis	-	0	3	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
edm	-	-	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
a-loc	-	-	-	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
ctlog	-	-	-	-	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
bio	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
lode	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0
eac-cpf	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	0
eclap	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	0
donto	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	1
time	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0

to respective fields of 8 out of the 12 (excluding the in-word vocabulary) vocabularies included in the analysis, while cis’s class “:Cultural Entity” could be mapped to classes of 6 other vocabularies.

Focusing on the X (CORE) mappings of the initial mapping matrix, Table 4 is a sample table of potential mappings between various vocabulary fields and fields belonging to core vocabularies. As explained earlier, most of the vocabularies under analysis did not have high reuse of core vocabulary fields (dct, skos, etc.), however, the cases of this table occurred mainly due to donto (Dataset Description Ontology), which predominantly reuses DCAT fields in its schema. So, Table 4 includes instances of potential mappings mostly (with a few instance exceptions belonging to other vocabularies) between donto and the other vocabularies, including how many of those mappings could be considered more or less likely (green and yellow respectively).

The conducted analysis aimed to offer an overall perception of how the identified mappings are distributed among the examined vocabularies and emphasise areas of focus and how these mappings

can contribute towards improved cross-domain reuse and semantic interoperability. Before a more comprehensive look into the analysis of the presented mapping results, the results of the additional step for the potential inclusion of LLMs in future continuations of this study are shown below.

4.1 Preliminary Assessment of the Mapping Process using GPT-4

In this section, we delve into a brief evaluation of the mapping process utilising GPT-3.5 and GPT-4. The objective was to evaluate the models’ capabilities in identifying similarities across various cultural heritage vocabularies under different conditions.

The outcomes from employing GPT 3.5 in this experiment were minimal across all criteria and conditions, showing negligible impact. In contrast, the results obtained from GPT 4 exhibited a notable pattern and a significantly better ability in matching class similarities. More specifically, GPT-4 exhibited a progressive pattern in its performance: the more in-prompt examples it was provided with, the more accurately it recognized similar classes. As

Table 3: The predominantly mapped fields of the various LOV and their relations to other vocabularies.

VOCAB	Important Fields	# of potential mappings to other vocabularies	# of X (green) mappings	# of X (CORE) mappings	# of vocabularies the field is mapped to
ecrm	E39_Actor	28	0	1 (yellow)	8
ecrm	E5_Event	10	7	0	5
ecrm	E78_Collection	7	5	0	5
ecrm	E21_Person	7	1	1 (green)	8
ecrm	E1_CRM_Entity	6	3	0	4
ecrm	E19_Physical_Object	6	0	0	4
ecrm	E52_Time-Span	6	1	1 (yellow)	5
ecrm	E42_Identifier	5	0	0	1
ecrm	E48_Place_Name	5	1	0	2
cevent	10:Entity	11	4	0	6
cevent	:TimePeriod	10	4	0	6
cevent	10:EventOrSituation	9	1	0	6
cevent	10:Collection	8	5	0	6
cis	:CulturalHeritageObject	10	1	0	5
cis	:CulturalEntity	10	3	0	6
cis	:TimeInterval	9	6	0	6
cis	:Event	9	7	0	5
cis	:Collection	8	7	0	6
edm	:Place	13	2	0	3
edm	:Event	9	7	0	5
edm	:TimeSpan	9	4	0	6
edm	:EuropeanaObject	6	0	0	5
a-loc	cis:CulturalInstituteOrSite	11	4	0	2
a-loc	cis:CulturalEntity	10	3	0	4
a-loc	core:TimeIndexedSituation	9	2	0	3
a-loc	l0:Collection	8	5	0	6
ctlog	tiapit:TimeInterval	12	7	0	8
ctlog	<http://dati.benicultur-ali.it/cis/CulturalEntity>	7	3	0	5
bio	<http://purl.org/vocab/bio/0.1/Event>	2	5	0	5
lode	leo:Event	7	6	0	4
eac-cpf	:entity	14	2	2 (yellow)	8
eac-cpf	:person	8	3	1 (yellow)	8
eac-cpf	:place	6	2	0	4
eclap	:Collection	7	4	0	5
eclap	:User	6	1	1 (yellow)	5
donto	:TimeInterval	8	4	2 (green)	6
donto	:SpatialThing	6	1	0	3
time	:Interval	9	2	0	8
time	:DateTimeInterval	9	0	0	7

the model was provided with an increasing number of in-prompt examples from the legal domain for learning, its performance based on F1 score progressively improved. In the zero-shot scenario, GPT 4 predicted only a minimal number of similarities. However, this improved with the three-shot approach, and there was a significant enhancement in the predictions when six examples were provided. This progression established a foundation, suggesting that learnings and patterns identified in one domain (the legal domain in this case)

could potentially be applied interchangeably to other knowledge domains. It aligned closely with the intuitions the authors followed in performing the mapping. These results underscore the potential of employing more Large Language Models (LLMs) to automate the process of mapping and to perform such tasks with greater ease across various domains. This is a sample case study which sets up the arena for more comprehensive research in the future to combine human expertise and machine intelligence for improved

Table 4: Instances of predominantly mapped fields to core vocabulary fields.

VOCAB Fields	Core fields	# of (core) vocabularies the field was mapped to	Green mappings	Yellow Mappings
ecrm: E21_Person	dct:Agent, foaf:Person	2	1	1
ecrm: E30_Right	dct:Jurisdiction, dct:LicenseDocument, dct:RightsStatement	3	1	2
ecrm: E4_Period	dct:PeriodOfTime	1	0	1
ecrm: E28_Conceptual_Object	skos:Concept	1	0	1
ecrm: E39_Actor	dct:AgentClass	1	0	1
ecrm: E52_Time-Span	dct:PeriodOfTime	1	0	1
ecrm: E40_Legal_Body	dct:Jurisdiction	1	0	1
ecrm: E56_Language	dct:LinguisticSystem	1	0	1
ecrm: E19_Physical_Object	dct:PhysicalMedium	1	0	1
ecrm: E32_Authority_Document	dct:LicenseDocument, dct:RightsStatement	2	0	2
cevent: core:Concept	core:Concept, skos:Concept	2	2	0
cevent: 10:Agent	dct:Agent	1	1	0
cis: :SubjectDiscipline	dct:SubjectScheme	1	0	1
cis: :Agent	dct:Agent	1	1	0
edm: :InformationResource	dct:BibliographicResource	1	1	0
edm: :Place	dct:Location	1	0	1
a-loc:Coordinates	dct:Location	1	1	0
eac-cpf: :person	foaf:Person	1	1	0
eac-cpf: :corporateBody	dct:Policy	1	0	1
time: :TemporalUnit	dct:PeriodOfTime	1	0	1
eclap: :Crossmedia	dct:MediaType	1	0	1

Table 5: Analysis of Zero-Shot Learning

VOCABS	cevent	cis	TP	FP	FN	TN	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
ecrm	3	3	2	4	23	128	0.33	0.08	0.129
cevent	0	3	3	0	22	132	0.5	0.12	0.193
cis	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	3	6	5	4	45	260	0.55	0.1	0.169

results and the ability to extend the experiments into more areas of application. A more detailed analysis of the various engineered prompt cases, highlighting the nuanced capabilities and potential applications of LLMs in this regard is presented next.

4.1.1 GPT-4 Zero-Shot Analysis. While exploring GPT-4’s zero-shot learning capabilities across various vocabularies, particular attention was paid to the aggregate F1 Score, which serves as a comprehensive measure of the model’s overall performance in balancing precision and recall. The cumulative F1 Score of 0.169, derived from the performance across all tested vocabularies, underscores the model’s general ability to identify relevant instances with moderate effectiveness. This overall F1 Score suggests that while GPT-4 exhibits a certain level of proficiency without prior direct examples, there remains room for optimization, especially in refining its precision-recall balance. The total F1 Score, as presented in Table 5, acts as a critical benchmark for evaluation, highlighting its potential and areas for enhancement in processing diverse vocabularies.

4.1.2 GPT-4 Three-Shot Analysis. Employing a three-shot learning, where GPT-4 was provided with three contextual examples, significantly influenced the model’s aggregate performance, particularly increasing F1 score observed across different vocabularies. This metric, pivotal for assessing the balance between precision and recall, saw an overarching enhancement, with the total F1 score reaching 0.257. This advancement underscores the efficacy of three-shot learning in refining the model’s ability to equally weigh its precision and recall, thereby improving its overall accuracy. Notably, the ‘cevent’ vocabulary demonstrated a superior F1 Score of 0.27, reflecting a significant leap in model performance without any false positives. Table 6 clearly demonstrates the advantages of using few-shot learning with GPT-4, specifically in its enhanced ability to identify and classify similar attributes accurately and effectively.

4.1.3 GPT-4 Six-Shot Analysis. In the six-shot learning, GPT-4 was given six examples to learn from, leading to significant improvements in its performance, particularly in terms of the F1 score. It

Table 6: Analysis of Fewshot (three) Learning

VOCABS	cevent	cis	TP	FP	FN	TN	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
ecrm	4	4	4	4	21	128	0.5	0.16	0.24
cevent	0	4	4	0	21	132	1	0.16	0.27
cis	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	4	8	8	4	42	260	0.66	0.16	0.257

Table 7: Analysis of Fewshot (six) Learning

VOCABS	cevent	cis	TP	FP	FN	TN	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
ecrm	10	11	6	15	19	117	0.28	0.24	0.258
cevent	0	8	7	1	18	131	0.875	0.28	0.42
cis	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	10	19	13	16	37	248	0.44	0.26	0.326

increased noticeably, reaching 0.326 overall. This improvement illustrates the effectiveness of six-shot learning in enhancing GPT-4’s ability to accurately identify similar attributes. In particular, the ‘cevent’ vocabulary saw a notable F1 score of 0.42, indicating a considerable increase in model accuracy without a corresponding increase in false positives. These results, detailed in Table 7, highlight the impact of providing GPT-4 with more examples, which significantly improves its efficiency. The six-shot scenario clearly demonstrates how increasing the number of contextual examples can positively affect GPT-4’s performance, thereby enhancing its capability to make more accurate and balanced classifications of similar attributes.

The preliminary assessment of the mapping process using GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 provided valuable insights into the capabilities for identifying similarities across diverse cultural heritage vocabularies. GPT-3.5 exhibited limited effectiveness in this task, while GPT-4 displayed substantial improvements, especially when provided with more examples for context. The progressive pattern observed in GPT-4’s performance, with better results in three-shot and six-shot learning scenarios, suggests its ability to leverage knowledge from the legal domain examples and apply it effectively to the cultural heritage domain. Despite some false positives, GPT-4’s ability to identify true positives and its F1 score increased significantly with more training examples, indicating the potential of LLMs like GPT-4 in aiding the mapping and comparison of complex vocabularies in the CH field. It reflected an upward trend of improved efficiency with more training examples and contextual knowledge. The progression of performance with increasing examples from the legal domain establishes the transferability of knowledge between different domains and lays a solid foundation for future research.

5 DISCUSSION

The results of the mapping process revealed several key aspects to be taken into consideration regarding the alignment of semantically adjacent vocabulary elements in the CH domain. Based on the analysis, a low reuse of existing domain-specific and core vocabulary fields was observed, a strong indication that there is

still plenty of room for improvement as far as semantically interoperable schemata within and across various domains is concerned. Moreover, linking semantically relatable vocabulary fields to established and standardised schemata (e.g., DCAT) could drastically make a difference. As the analysis showed, a number of elements of each vocabulary could potentially be mapped to elements of a big number of the other vocabularies (usually more than half), a demonstration of already existing relationships that have not yet been officially established on a semantic level. The experiment performed in this study showed that relationships among closely or remotely related fields of knowledge are feasible to identify by combining analyses of more than one knowledge domain. For instance, half of the vocabularies methodologically chosen for this study are not directly integrated in the CH domain, sharing however a lot of commonalities with the first half which can be considered CH vocabularies per se, thus forming the nucleus of this research in the quest for more cross-domain interoperable data.

These existing conceptual similarities play a critical role not only in an intra-vocabulary context (as the relationships in this case are usually taken care of in the respective data or metadata schema) but in an inter-domain context where we shift from conventional domain-specific knowledge representation towards cross-domain interoperable data, although the special traits of one knowledge domain are, understandably, not to be ignored. Knowledge representation takes place in various hierarchical levels, each of them including a number or related vocabularies and ontologies with some of them spanning across a wider spectrum of hierarchical details of information. For instance, in the CH domain, the ecrm vocabulary (an implementation of CIDOC-CRM) contains elements which provide a much higher level of specificity compared to other vocabularies of the same domain, including a larger variety of specified annotations for adjacent concepts, achieving higher accuracy in artifact description. Due to this characteristic, semantic mapping processes are more difficult to distinguish or there can be various cases of one-to-many mappings. The conceptual levels of hierarchy need to be respected to avoid the risk of losing important information but at the same time allowing for flexibility within and across

the knowledge domain, something which entails the need for more sophisticated means of links identification and mapping.

In this light, apart from the manual mapping process which is understandably only applicable for a smaller sample of links and vocabularies, the authors aimed to bring together the concept of automated processes under the same purpose, e.g., LLM-inclusive methodological approaches to expand the potential for this domain. The authors assessed the interchangeability of knowledge between domains using LLMs and elicited promising insights which set the foundation for further research towards the implementation of automated methods to map large numbers of vocabularies. A successful and well-targeted implementation of an automated or a semi-automated combination of methods could bring forth the advantages of mapping larger numbers of vocabularies and ontologies of similar or different domains in order to facilitate the transition from conventional domain-specific knowledge representation to reusable and semantically interoperable information.

6 LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

All things considered; the proposed approach is subject to some limitations. To begin with, the outcome of the manual mapping needs further validation. The initial results presented in this study are solely evaluated by the authors, so there might be ambiguity in the mapping of certain fields of the vocabularies, including the cases of fields where no sufficient information was provided in the schema. As mentioned earlier, mappings of second or third (and so forth) degree relations are too complex to consider in a manual process performed by solely human actors and require the assistance of algorithmic intervention, so these cases could be dealt with in future progressions of this study. In the present study, the cases with no or very little information were not considered, however, manual mapping is prone to human error, due to the vast number of pairwise comparisons and sensitivity to subjective interpretation. On the other hand, for cases with a small sample of vocabularies, the manual mapping possesses benefits not otherwise present in the case of automated ways, (e.g., human expertise for cases where the relations are not obvious and require prior or domain-specific knowledge). For this reason, the continuation of the presented work aims to include methods for further validation of the semantic mapping results, which involve both human (expert opinions until consensus) and non-human (machine learning) approaches. In addition, the possibility to involve the training of large language models (LLMs) and the design of one LLM focusing specifically on this knowledge domain is also under consideration.

Another aspect to consider regarding this study is that, due to the complex relations and vastness of information, only the classes of the vocabularies were considered, and the method was applied on a sample of 12 chosen vocabularies, as was described in the Method Section. Future continuation of this study aims to include a more comprehensive analysis of relations (including 2nd, 3rd and further- degree relations) of the vocabularies and will involve all 104 LOV vocabularies identified initially, which were impossible to include in the manual analysis. The mapping is also currently rather incomplete due to the lack of information for the description of a significant number of classes of the analysed vocabularies. Moreover, considering that the ultimate goal of this study is to facilitate

the shift towards cross-domain linking of data, further research following this study might involve more sophisticated methodologies for the inclusion of vocabularies of clearly different areas in order to continue the extension of this smaller-scale experiment towards other domains of focus, demonstrating the relations and reusability of certain elements spanning across a number of different (closely or remotely related) knowledge domains.

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